

The Effect of *Perceived Quality* and *Price Perception* on *Repurchase Intention* through *Satisfaction* (Study on Glad2Glow Brand *Skincare* Customers on Shopee)

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the effect of Perceived Quality and Price Perception on Repurchase Intention through Satisfaction among customers of the Glad2Glow skincare brand on Shopee. The study is motivated by the increasing competition in the skincare industry, which requires companies to understand the factors influencing customers' repurchase intentions. This research adopts a quantitative approach using a survey method involving 146 respondents who have purchased Glad2Glow moisturizer products through the official Shopee store. Data analysis was conducted using Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The results indicate that Perceived Quality has a significant effect on Repurchase Intention, while Price Perception does not have a significant effect on Repurchase Intention. In addition, both Perceived Quality and Price Perception significantly affect Satisfaction, and Satisfaction significantly affects Repurchase Intention. Satisfaction is proven to act as a mediating variable in the relationship between Perceived Quality and Price Perception toward Repurchase Intention.

Keywords: Perceived Quality, Price Perception, Satisfaction, Repurchase Intention, Glad2Glow, Shopee, SEM-PLS.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of the *e-commerce* industry in Indonesia in recent years has shown a great contribution to the growth of the national digital economy. The value of Indonesia's digital economy in 2022 is projected to reach USD 77 billion with an annual growth of 22%. Of these, the *e-commerce* sector contributes the largest value, which is USD 59 billion and is estimated to increase to USD 95 billion by 2025 (Komdigi, 2023). This condition shows that *e-commerce* is the main sector in encouraging digital-based economic activities in Indonesia.

Entering 2025, the competition for *e-commerce platforms* in Indonesia is getting tighter. Some of the platforms that dominate the market are Shopee, Tokopedia, TikTok Shop, and Lazada (GoodStats, 2025a). Based on APJII data, Shopee occupies the first position as the most frequently accessed platform for Indonesians with a percentage of 53.22% (GoodStats, 2025b). Shopee's dominance is supported by an aggressive marketing strategy, daily promos, ease of digital payments, and a fast logistics system so that it is the main choice of customers.

The increasing use of the internet and changes in people's

behavior that tend to shop online make *e-commerce* an important distribution channel, including in the cosmetics and *skincare* industries (digima, 2025). The cosmetics industry is a fast-growing sector with great potential in Indonesia (kompas.id, 2024). In July 2025, Shopee managed to become the market leader in the *beauty e-commerce* category in Indonesia with a GMV contribution of 60%, followed by TikTok Shop and Tokopedia of 34%, and Lazada (Scaler, 2025). This shows that Shopee has a strong position in the sale of beauty products.

This dominance is influenced by increasing public awareness of the importance of skin care, especially among the younger generation. The survey shows that 86% of Gen Z consider the use of *skincare* more important than *makeup* (Suara.com, 2024). This phenomenon drives the demand for beauty products, both local and international brands. However, local products are still the main choice of the Indonesian people. As many as 87% of millennials and Gen Z use local *skincare* products, while South Korea is 31%, Japan is 16%, and the United States is 5% (Populix, 2025). This condition shows high consumer confidence in the quality of domestic products.

The advantages of local products are also supported by the perception of quality and competitive prices. The Populix survey stated that 57% of respondents rated the quality of local products quite good and 29% rated them as very good (GoodStats, 2024). In addition, the price of local products tends to be more affordable than foreign products (kompas.com, 2020). This is a great opportunity for local brands to expand the market and increase competitiveness.

Various types of *skincare* products available on the market include *face masks, serums, toners, sunscreens, eyecreams, cleansers, and moisturizers* (Alodokter, 2023). Based on Populix data (2025), the most widely used products by the Indonesian people are *cleanser* at 63%, followed by *sunscreen* at 54%, and *moisturizer* at 51%. Even though it is under *cleanser* and *sunscreen*, *moisturizer* is an important product because it functions to maintain skin moisture and strengthen the *skin barrier* (Alodokter, 2024). Therefore, *moisturizers* were chosen as the object of research because they are an important part of the *skincare* routine.

Some of the *moisturizer* brands that dominate the Shopee market are Skintific, Glad2Glow, and Wardah (VRITimes, 2024). In the Top 3 Brand category, Skintific has a *market share* of 10.78%, Glad2Glow 8.12%, and Wardah 5.62%. This shows that Glad2Glow as a newcomer brand is able to compete with old and foreign brands. Glad2Glow is also interesting because it targets the Gen Z and millennial market through various product variants according to the needs of the age of consumers (Kumparan.id, 2025).

In terms of price, Glad2Glow offers the most affordable *moisturizer* products compared to its competitors. The price of the Glad2Glow Moisturizer Series 30g is IDR 37,430, lower than Wardah IDR 49,440, CeraVe IDR 54,500, The Ordinary IDR 73,858, and Skintific IDR 108,800. This price strategy provides added value for consumers who want quality products at economical prices. In addition, production in China allows Glad2Glow to reduce costs so that it can compete in the market (Kompas.id, 2025).

The quality of Glad2Glow products is also reflected in the rating of 4.9/5 on the *official* Shopee store with *moisturizer* sales reaching 277,900 units. Many customer reviews say that this product is able to moisturize the skin, make the skin texture smoother, and has a low price with satisfactory quality. Positive perceptions about quality and price can increase customer satisfaction and encourage *repurchase intention*.

According to Kotler and Keller (2016), *Repurchase Intention* is influenced by satisfaction, *performance quality*, and price perception. Hoyer et al. (2020) also explain that quality, satisfaction, and loyalty play a role in driving repurchases. Based on this theory, the variables *Perceived Quality* and *Price Perception* were chosen as independent variables, while *Satisfaction* was used as the mediation variable. However, the results of previous research still show inconsistencies. Some studies state that *Perceived Quality* and *Price Perception* have a significant effect on *Repurchase Intention*, while other studies show the opposite result. This indicates that there is a *research gap* that needs to be re-researched.

In addition, the market share of *Glad2Glow moisturizer* on

Shopee during 2023–2025 shows fluctuations. In September 2023, the market share reached 8.7%, decreased to 5.1% in the second quarter of 2024, rose to 8.12% in the third quarter of 2024, fell again to 7.28% in the first quarter of 2025, and then rose to 7.7% in the second quarter of 2025. These changes show that consumer repurchase decisions have an important role in maintaining market share stability.

Based on this phenomenon, research on the influence of *Perceived Quality* and *Price Perception* on *Repurchase Intention* through *Satisfaction* in Glad2Glow brand *skincare* customers is important. This research is expected to make a theoretical and practical contribution to companies in designing marketing strategies, increasing customer satisfaction, and maintaining consumer loyalty.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Consumer Behavior

Consumer behavior is an important concept in marketing because it relates to how consumers make decisions about products or services. Hoyer et al. (2020) explained that *consumer behavior* reflects all consumer decisions related to the acquisition, consumption, and disposal of goods, services, activities, experiences, people, and ideas. Indrasari (2019) states that consumer behavior is the action of individuals who are directly involved in obtaining, using, and determining products or services. Meanwhile, Solomon et al. (2024) view consumer behavior as the study of the process of choosing, buying, using, and disposing of products, services, ideas, or experiences to meet needs and express one's identity. Kotler and Keller (2016) also emphasized that consumer behavior is the study of how individuals, groups, and organizations choose, buy, use, and dispose of goods or services to meet their needs and desires. Based on these various opinions, consumer behavior can be interpreted as the actions and processes carried out by consumers in obtaining, using, and evaluating products or services.

The consumer behavior model according to Engel and Blackwell (1995) explains that the purchase decision is a process that starts from the recognition of needs, search for information, evaluation of alternatives, purchase decisions, to the final result in the form of satisfaction or dissatisfaction. At the stage of recognition of needs, consumers are aware of the gap between current conditions and desired conditions. Furthermore, consumers are looking for information from both internal and external sources. After that, consumers evaluate various alternatives based on benefits, features, and prices. The next stage is purchase, which is the final decision in choosing a particular product. After purchase, consumers evaluate whether the product is up to expectations. If it is appropriate, then satisfaction arises, while if it is not appropriate, dissatisfaction will appear.

In the digital context, online consumer behavior according to Turban et al. (2017) is influenced by two groups of factors, namely *Uncontrollable Variables* and *Controllable Variables*. *Uncontrollable Variables* include consumer characteristics, environmental factors, and the conditions of traders and competitors. Meanwhile, *Controllable Variables* are factors that a company can control, such as the online sales system, product/service quality, and price. In this study, the variables

Perceived Quality and *Price Perception* came from factors that the company could control, while *Repurchase Intention* was related to customer loyalty behavior.

According to Taghipourian and Bakhsh (2015), consumer loyalty develops through four stages, namely *cognitive loyalty*, *affective loyalty*, *conative loyalty*, and *action loyalty*. At the cognitive stage, loyalty is formed due to the belief that the brand is superior to competitors. The affective stage arises due to the presence of likes and satisfaction with the brand. The conative stage indicates a strong intention to buy back in the future. The last stage is real action in the form of consistent repurchases. Thus, *Repurchase Intention* is at the *conative loyalty stage* because it is still in the form of a repurchase intention, not yet a real behavior.

According to Yum and Kim (2024), consumer loyalty is influenced by two main factors, namely *Perceived Value* and *Customer Satisfaction*. Consumers will be loyal if the benefits received are greater than the costs incurred and feel satisfied with the products or services used.

2.2. Repurchase Intention

Repurchase Intention is the consumer's intention to buy back a product or brand after having previous use experience. Hawkins and Mothersbaugh (2010) state that repurchase intent arises after consumers use the product and feel satisfaction. Thamrin and Francis (2016) add that repurchase intent is based on previous purchase experience. Thus, *Repurchase Intention* is the tendency of consumers to return to buy the same product because of previous positive experiences.

Hoyer et al. (2021) explained that repurchase intent is influenced by several factors, namely *Perceived Quality*, *Satisfaction*, and *Customer Loyalty*. Products that are perceived as quality will increase the positive evaluation of consumers. Customer satisfaction is also an important factor because satisfied consumers tend to buy back and recommend products. Additionally, loyalty strengthens the long-term relationship between consumers and brands.

Kotler and Keller (2016) mentioned other psychological factors that affect *Repurchase Intention*, namely *Price Perception*, *Perceived Quality*, and *Perceived Value*. Consumers tend to make a repeat purchase if the price is considered reasonable, good quality, and the benefits received are proportional to the costs incurred.

Based on several previous studies, indicators of *Repurchase Intention* include repurchase intent, the tendency to choose the same brand, and the desire to continue using the product in the future (Ding et al., 2022). In this study, the indicators used were the intention to buy back Glad2Glow moisturizer in the near future, the tendency to buy again, and the desire to continue using the product in the future.

2.3. Perceived Quality

Perceived Quality is the consumer's perception of the overall quality of a product or service compared to their expectations. Putri et al. (2021) stated that *Perceived Quality* is the value that consumers perceive from a brand based on reliability, product excellence, and service as a whole. Hawkins and Mothersbaugh (2010) explain that perceived quality arises from a comparison between the actual performance of the product and the consumer's initial expectations. If performance exceeds

expectations, consumers will rate the quality high.

Hazen et al. (2017) categorized the *Perceived Quality* indicator into three dimensions, namely *lifespan*, *performance*, and *serviceability*. *Lifespan* is related to the durability or reliability of the product. *Performance* relates to the ability of a product to perform its main function. *Serviceability* is related to ease of service, seller response, or after-sales support.

In this study, the *Perceived Quality* indicators used include the ability of Glad2Glow moisturizer to moisturize the skin, safety of use before expiration, product reliability, conformity of content with specifications, fulfillment of product standards, and quality of official store services at Shopee.

2.4. Price Perception

Price Perception is a consumer's assessment of the price of a product based on the benefits and quality received. Aaker (1996) explained that price perception is related to consumers' willingness to pay more or expect lower prices than competitors who offer similar benefits. Kotler and Armstrong (2018) stated that price perception is a consumer evaluation of whether the price of a product is acceptable according to the value given. If the price is considered too high for the benefits, consumers are less likely to buy.

Some of the *Price Perception* indicators that are often used are price affordability, price suitability with benefits, price suitability with quality, and price competitiveness (Yasri et al., 2020). In this study, the indicators used include the affordability of the price of Glad2Glow moisturizer, the suitability of the price with the benefits obtained, and the suitability of the price with the quality of the product.

2.5. Satisfaction

Satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure or disappointment that arises after consumers compare initial expectations with the actual performance of the product. Wardhana (2024) states that satisfaction is the consumer's feelings towards the product or service that has been purchased and used. Kotler and Keller (2016) explain that satisfaction is an emotional response in the form of pleasure after comparing the perceived results with previous expectations. Thus, satisfaction is a consumer's evaluation of the product's user experience.

Indrasari (2019) explained that satisfaction is influenced by product quality, service quality, emotional factors, prices, and costs incurred. Quality products, good service, appropriate prices, and low additional costs will increase customer satisfaction.

Some of the indicators of *Satisfaction* according to Mansori (2016) and Uzir et al. (2020) include the suitability of expectations, satisfaction with the purchase decision, confidence that the choice is right, and willingness to recommend the product. In this study, the indicators used were the suitability of expectations for the Glad2Glow moisturizer and satisfaction with the decision to buy the product.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a type of conclusive research, namely research that focuses on hypothesis testing, explaining the relationship between variables, and providing information for quantitative decision-making (Malhotra & Dash, 2016). This type was chosen

because the study aims to analyze the influence of Perceived Quality and Price Perception on Repurchase Intention through Satisfaction as a mediating variable. The research design used is causal research, which is a design used to prove causal relationships between research variables (Malhotra & Dash, 2016).

The source of research data comes from primary data, namely data obtained directly from respondents through research instruments in the form of questionnaires (Malhotra & Dash, 2016). Respondents are consumers who have bought and used Glad2Glow moisturizer through the official store on Shopee. The research was conducted online by distributing online questionnaires through digital media such as X, TikTok, Instagram, and WhatsApp.

The data collection technique uses a survey method with a questionnaire instrument, which is a structured set of questions to obtain information from respondents (Malhotra & Dash, 2016). The questionnaire is compiled through Google Form, distributed online using a link or QR Code, then the results are automatically stored in a digital database.

The data analysis technique uses Partial Least Square-Structural

Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM), which is a method to analyze the relationships between latent variables in complex models simultaneously (Rahadi, 2023). Model evaluation is carried out through two stages, namely the outer model and the inner model. The mediation test in this study refers to Zhao et al. (2010), which divided the results of mediation into several forms, namely Complementary mediation, Competitive mediation, Indirect-only mediation, and Direct-only nonmediation, according to the direct and indirect relationship between variables through mediators.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Overview of Research Objects

In this study is the Glad2Glow brand moisturizer, which is a moisturizing skincare product that is known to have a lightweight, fast-absorbing, and affordable formula. This product is intended for various skin problems such as dull, acne-prone, and sensitive skin. The active ingredients used include *niacinamide*, *centella asiatica*, *ceramide*, and *retinol* which function to provide hydration, brighten the skin, soothe irritation, and help improve the skin barrier.

Figure 4.1 Moisturizer Glad2Glow

Glad2Glow has several moisturizer variants, such as Pomegranate 5% Niacinamide Brightening Moisturizer, Yuja Symwhite 377 Dark Spot Moisturizer, and Blueberry 5% Ceramide Barrier Repair Moisturizer. Each variant offers different benefits so that customers can choose products according to their individual skin needs.

This product was chosen as the object of research because it has interesting market characteristics. Glad2Glow targets Generation Z to Millennial consumers, especially 13–30 years old. For adolescents to young adults, variants with *soothing*, *acne care*, *brightening*, and *barrier repair functions* are available. Meanwhile, for consumers around 30 years old, there are products that are tailored to the needs of the skin in that age range.

In addition to market segmentation, the appeal of Glad2Glow also lies in its production strategy and price. Even though it is a local brand, the production process is carried out in China so that production costs can be reduced. This strategy allows the

company to offer moisturizers at a more affordable price than some competitors, while still providing quality that is considered satisfactory by customers. The combination of product variety, wide target market, and competitive price makes Glad2Glow moisturizer relevant for further research.

4.2 Research Results

The results of this study aim to test the influence of Perceived Quality and Price Perception on Repurchase Intention with Satisfaction as a mediating variable. Data was obtained through the distribution of questionnaires from November 23, 2025 to January 12, 2026 and collected 146 respondents who met the research criteria. All data was collected online through barcodes and analyzed using Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with the help of SmartPLS version 4 because it is suitable for causal research with models that involve direct or indirect relationships between variables.

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents

Respondent Characteristics		Quantity	Percentage
Gender	Male	30	20.55%
	Women	116	79.45%
Total		146	100%
Age	13-17 Years	21	14.38%
	18-23 Years	111	76.03%
	24-29 Years	10	6.85%
	30 Years	4	2.74%
Total		146	100.00%
Education Level	Junior High School Equivalent	10	6.85%
	High School Equivalent	42	28.77%
	Diploma	7	4.79%
	Bachelor	82	56.16%
	Postgraduate	5	3.42%
Total		146	100.00%
Revenue	< IDR 500,000	36	24.66%
	IDR 500,000 - IDR 1,000,000	34	23.29%
	IDR 1,000,001 - IDR 1,500,000	22	15.07%
	IDR 1,500,001 - IDR 2,000,000	20	13.70%
	> Rp 2.000.000	34	23.29%
Total		146	100.00%

Source : Processed by the researcher

Based on the characteristics of respondents, the majority of respondents were female as many as 116 people (79.45%), while men were 30 people (20.55%). In terms of age, respondents were dominated by the 18-23 year old group as many as 111 people (76.03%), while the 30-year-old was only 4 people (2.74%). Based on education, the majority are 82 Bachelor graduates (56.16%), while 5 are Postgraduate graduates (3.42%). In terms

of income, the largest group had an income below IDR 500,000 as many as 36 people (24.66%), while the least was in the range of IDR 1,500,001 – IDR 2,000,000 as many as 20 people (13.70%). In general, respondents are dominated by young women with bachelor's education levels and low to medium income.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

Statement Items	Scale					Total	Mean	Ket.
	1	2	3	4	5			
Perceived Quality (X1)								
X1.1.1	1	7	22	82	34	146	3.996	Setuju
X1.1.2	0	2	19	67	58	146	4.240	Strongly agree
X1.1.3	0	3	18	73	52	146	4.192	Setuju
X1.1.4	0	8	24	74	40	146	4.001	Setuju
X1.2.1	0	1	20	80	45	146	4.158	Setuju
X1.2.2	0	1	18	74	53	146	4.226	Strongly agree
X1.2.3	1	1	14	59	71	146	4.356	Strongly agree

Statement Items	Scale					Total	Mean	Ket.
	1	2	3	4	5			
X1.3.1	0	5	14	60	67	146	4.295	Strongly agree
X1.3.2	2	4	24	68	48	146	4.070	Setuju
Price Perception (X2)								
X2.1.1	0	5	14	60	67	146	4,294	Strongly agree
X2.2.1	0	3	19	74	50	146	4,171	Setuju
X2.3.1	2	4	24	68	48	146	4,068	Setuju
X2.3.2	2	5	18	75	46	146	4,082	Setuju
Satisfaction (W)								
Z1.1.1	0	8	24	72	42	146	4,013	Setuju
Z1.2.1	1	5	19	74	47	146	4,102	Setuju
Z1.2.2	2	4	19	74	47	146	4,095	Setuju
Repurchase Intention (Y1)								
Y1.1.1	2	19	24	60	34	139	3,755	Setuju
Y1.1.2	2	12	30	26	32	139	3,798	Setuju
Y1.1.3	0	6	26	75	32	139	3,956	Setuju

Source: Smart PLS 4 (Processed by researcher)

The respondents' assessment used a five-point Likert scale with a category interval ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree (Zebua et al., 2010). In the Perceived Quality variable, all items received a positive rating. The highest average score was found in item X1.2.3, namely "Glad2Glow brand moisturizer meets the standard" with a mean of 4,356 (Strongly Agree). The lowest value is found in item X1.1.1, which is the ability to moisturize the skin to the maximum with a mean of 3.996 (Agree). These results show that respondents rated the quality of Glad2Glow products well and met the expected standards.

In the Price Perception variable, the item with the highest mean is X2.1.1, which is the perception that the price of the product is affordable with a value of 4.294 (Strongly Agree). The lowest value is found in item X2.3.1, where the price reflects the quality of the product with a mean of 4,068 (Agree). These findings show that the main strength of Glad2Glow lies in the price that is considered affordable, while the price compatibility with quality remains positively rated despite being relatively lower.

In the Satisfaction variable, the highest score was obtained for item Z1.2.1, namely satisfaction with the decision to buy a product with a mean of 4.102 (Agree). The lowest value is found

in item Z1.1.1, which is that the product meets expectations with a mean of 4.013 (Agree). This shows that the majority of respondents feel satisfied after purchasing and using Glad2Glow moisturizer.

In the Repurchase Intention variable, the highest value is found in item Y1.1.3, namely the intention to continue purchases in the future with a mean of 3.956 (Agree). The lowest value is found in item Y1.1.1, which is the intention to buy back in the near future with a mean of 3.755 (Agree). These findings show that respondents have a tendency to make repurchases, especially for the long term, although the intention to buy back in the near future is still influenced by certain considerations.

4.3 Data Analysis

This study analyzed data using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on Partial Least Squares (PLS-SEM) through SmartPLS version 4.0 with 146 respondents. The test was carried out in two stages, namely the outer model to assess the quality of the indicator and the inner model to test the relationship between latent variables. According to Hair et al. (2022), this approach is suitable for prediction-oriented research and model development.

Table 3. Outer Model Measurements

Variabel	Statement Items	Outer Loading	AVE	CA	CR
<i>Perceived Quality (X1)</i>	X1.1.1	0,766	0,573	0,907	0,911
	X1.1.2	0,782			
	X1.1.3	0,709			
	X1.1.4	0,739			
	X1.2.1	0,789			
	X1.2.2	0,758			
	X1.2.3	0,763			
	X1.3.1	0,766			
	X1.3.2	0,735			
<i>Price Perception (X2)</i>	X2.1.1	0,617	0,692	0,885	0,887
	X2.2.1	0,874			
	X2.3.1	0,902			
	X2.3.2	0,900			
<i>Repurchase Intention (Y1)</i>	Y1.1.1	0,899	0,808	0,881	0,881
	Y1.1.2	0,919			
	Y1.1.3	0,877			
<i>Satisfaction (Z1)</i>	Z1.1.1	0,869	0,815	0,886	0,886
	Z1.2.1	0,926			
	Z1.2.2	0,913			

Source : Smart PLS 4 (Processed by the researcher)

At the measurement model (outer model) stage, testing is carried out to ensure the validity and reliability of the indicators. A good outer loading value is ≥ 0.70 because it shows that the indicator is able to explain more than 50% of the construct variance (Hair et al., 2022). The variables Perceived Quality, Repurchase Intention, and Satisfaction all have indicators above the minimum limit. In the Price Perception variable, there is one indicator, namely X2.1.1 with a value of 0.617. However, the indicator can still be maintained because the values of AVE, Composite Reliability (CR), and Cronbach's Alpha (CA) still meet the construct feasibility criteria. In general, all constructs are declared valid and suitable for use.

The reliability test showed that all variables had a Composite Reliability value above 0.70 and below 0.95, namely Perceived Quality 0.911, Price Perception 0.887, Repurchase Intention 0.881, and Satisfaction 0.886. According to Hair et al. (2019), these values indicate good internal consistency without any indicator redundancy. Thus, the research instrument is relatively reliable.

The validity of the convergence was tested through the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value and the loading factor. According to Ghozali (2021), a good loading factor value is above 0.70, while Hair et al. (2022) stated that the AVE value is at least 0.50. The results showed that the AVE value of the entire construct was above the minimum limit, namely Perceived Quality 0.573, Price Perception 0.692, Repurchase Intention 0.808, and Satisfaction 0.815. This shows that the entire construct has good convergent validity.

The validity of the discriminant was tested using the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT). According to Henseler et al. (2016), the construct is clearly different if the HTMT value is well below 1. The results showed that all HTMT values were between 0.707 to 0.896. The highest value is found in the relationship between Satisfaction and Repurchase Intention at 0.896, while the lowest in the relationship between Repurchase Intention and Price Perception is 0.707. Thus, the validity of the discrimination has been fulfilled.

Table 4. VIF Values

X1	LIVE	X2	LIVE	Y1	LIVE	Z1	LIVE
(X1.1.1).	2.329	(X2.1.1).	1.424	(Y1.1.1)	2.667	(Z1.1.1).	2.004
		(X2.2.1).	2.367				
(X1.1.2).	2.501	(X2.3.1).	3.193	(Y1.1.2).	3.110	(Zeph1.2.1).	3.428

(X1.1.3).	1.824	(X2.3.2).	3.108	(Y1.1.3)	2.102	(Z1.2.2).	3.196
(X1.1.4).	1.972						
(X1.2.1).	2.872						
(X1.2.2).	2.682						
(X1.2.3).	2.256						
(X1.3.1).	3.385						
(X1.3.2).	3.094						

Source : Smart PLS 4 (Processed by the researcher)

In the structural model (inner model) stage, the collinearity test is carried out using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). All indicators have a VIF value below 5, so the model is free from multicollinearity problems. The VIF value on Perceived Quality is between 1,824–3,385, Price Perception 2,024–3,193, Repurchase Intention 2,102–3,110, and Satisfaction 2,004–3,428. This suggests the entire construct can be reliably used in the model (Hair et al., 2022).

The R² value is used to see the model's predictive capabilities. Hair et al. (2019) categorized the values of 0.75 as substantial, 0.50 moderate, and 0.25 weak. The results showed that Satisfaction had an R² of 0.653, meaning that 65.3% of the satisfaction variation was explained by exogenous variables in the model. While Repurchase Intention has an R² of 0.595, meaning that 59.5% of the variation in repurchase intent can be explained by the model. Both of these values show good predictive ability.

Table 5. Indirect Influence Test

Relationships between variables	Original sample	Sample mean	t statistics	p values	Results
X1 -> Z -> Y	0,286	0,290	4,095	0,000	Signifikan
X2 -> Z -> Y	0,198	0,195	3,004	0,003	Signifikan

Source: Smart PLS 4 (Processed by researcher)

The size of the f² effect indicates the strength of the influence between variables. According to Hair et al. (2022), the value of 0.02 is relatively small, 0.15 medium, and 0.35 large. Model fit was tested using Standardized Root Mean Square

Residual (SRMR). According to Hair et al. (2022), SRMR values below 0.08 indicate a fit model. This study obtained an SRMR value of 0.074, so that the model has a good level of suitability and is suitable for further analysis.

Table 6. Summary of Path Coefficient Test Results

Hipotesis	Influence	Results
H1: <i>Perceived Quality</i> memengaruhi <i>Repurchase Intention</i>	Signifikan	Accepted
H2: <i>Price Perception</i> memengaruhi <i>Repurchase Intention</i>	Insignifikan	Not Accepted
H3: <i>Perceived Quality</i> memengaruhi <i>Satisfaction</i>	Signifikan	Accepted
H4: <i>Price Perception</i> Affects <i>Satisfaction</i>	Signifikan	Accepted
H5: <i>Satisfaction</i> memengaruhi <i>Repurchase Intention</i>	Signifikan	Accepted

Source : (Processed by researcher)

Based on the approach of Zhao et al. (2010), the relationship between Perceived Quality and Repurchase Intention through Satisfaction includes complementary mediation, because direct and indirect influences are equally significant. Meanwhile, the

relationship between Price Perception and Repurchase Intention through Satisfaction is classified as indirect-only mediation, because the direct influence is not significant but the indirect influence is significant. Thus, Satisfaction is an important variable

in increasing the repurchase intention of Glad2Glow customers.

4.3 Discussion

The results of the study are discussed by relating the findings to previous theories and research. In addition, this section also shows the difference in results that can be the basis for further research development.

Perceived Quality is proven to have a positive effect on Repurchase Intention, so H1 is accepted. This finding is in accordance with the theory of Kotler and Keller (2016) that the quality perceived by customers is an important factor in product evaluation. If the product is rated good and able to meet expectations, then the intention to buy again will increase. These results are in line with Haeruddin (2025), Gün and Söyük (2025), and Mardatilla Azzahra (2025). However, these results are different from Purnamasari and Fadli (2024) and Tuinesia et al. (2022) who found no significant effect. The difference is suspected to be because the object of the previous study was more general, while this study focused on the Glad2Glow moisturizer so that respondents were more specific in assessing the quality of the product. The majority of respondents consider Glad2Glow to have met the standards, especially in terms of moisture and packaging, although the effectiveness of moisture has not been felt equally by all users. Thus, Perceived Quality is the main factor in increasing Repurchase Intention.

Price Perception has no significant effect on Repurchase Intention, so H2 is rejected. This finding can be explained through Marshall's (1890) theory of elasticity, that in products with inelastic demand, price changes do not affect the purchase decision much. In the context of skincare, customers who are already compatible with the product consider the benefits and experience of use more than the price. This is supported by Kompas.id (2025), Alinea.id (2024), and ESQNews (2024). These results are in line with Nabilla and Rizky (2023) and Fauziah and Elwisam (2023), but different from Witoelar et al. (2024). These differences are influenced by the type of product and consumption patterns. The majority of respondents consider the price of Glad2Glow to be affordable, but the perception of the price is not strong enough to encourage direct repurchase intentions.

Perceived Quality has a significant positive effect on Satisfaction, so H3 is accepted. This shows that the better the perceived quality, the higher the customer satisfaction. These findings support Gultom et al. (2021). However, these results differ from Yolanda et al. (2019) and Jeong et al. (2019), as previous research focused on event services and experiences, while this study examined tangible products that are used regularly. Respondents rated the quality of Glad2Glow as standard and able to provide a moisturizing effect, although results still varied between users. In general, customers feel that the purchase decision is right and in line with expectations, although there is still room to improve product performance consistency.

Price Perception also has a significant positive effect on Satisfaction, so H4 is accepted. These findings are in line with Fais et al. (2019), Azmy (2024), Pritami and Suroño (2024), and Maharani (2024). However, in contrast to Suryawardana et al. (2023) who found it insignificant. These differences are influenced by product characteristics, because moisturizers are

used regularly so that customers pay more attention to the suitability of price and benefits. Respondents found the price of Glad2Glow to be affordable, although the perception that the price fully reflects the quality is still lower. In general, customers are still satisfied with the purchase transaction.

Satisfaction has a significant positive effect on Repurchase Intention, so H5 is accepted. These findings support the theory of Zikmund et al. (2003) that satisfaction is related to loyalty, which drives repurchase intent at the conative stage according to Taghipourian and Bakhsh (2015). These results are in line with Gusnandar and Untoro (2016), Ismoyo and Hadiwidjojo (2017), Afinia and Tjahjaningsih (2024), Rachmawati and Prapanca (2024), and Haeruddin (2025). However, it is different from Fausta et al. (2023). In this study, customers who are satisfied with the benefits and purchasing decisions tend to have the intention to buy again in the future, even though repurchases in the near future are still influenced by personal needs and the rest of the products they have.

Satisfaction is proven to mediate the influence of Perceived Quality on Repurchase Intention. This means that good product quality increases customer satisfaction, and then that satisfaction encourages repurchase intent. These results support Jauwena (2023) and Gultom et al. (2021), but are different from Purnamasari and Fadli (2024). Practically, Glad2Glow needs to maintain product quality, especially moisturizing ability, texture comfort, absorbability, and compatibility with various skin types. Satisfaction also mediates the influence of Price Perception on Repurchase Intention. Prices that are considered affordable can increase satisfaction, then that satisfaction encourages repurchase intentions. These findings are in line with Wigih Meifina Diyah Pangesti (2024) and Syahdina and Muslim (2025), but different from Noviandari and Fachroddi (2024). Practically, Glad2Glow needs to manage a pricing strategy that matches the benefits of the product in order to be able to create satisfaction and increase Repurchase Intent.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

Based on the results of the study on the effect of Perceived Quality and Price Perception on Repurchase Intention through Satisfaction in Glad2Glow brand skincare customers on Shopee, it can be concluded that Perceived Quality has a significant positive effect on Repurchase Intention. This means that the better the quality of the product that customers feel, the higher the intention to make a repurchase. Price Perception has no significant effect on Repurchase Intention. This shows that price perception is not the main factor that directly drives customer repurchase intent for Glad2Glow moisturizer products. Perceived Quality has a significant positive effect on Satisfaction. The quality of the product that meets customer expectations is able to increase the level of satisfaction after using Glad2Glow moisturizer. Price Perception has a significant positive effect on Satisfaction. Prices that are considered affordable and commensurate with the benefits of the product can create customer satisfaction. Satisfaction has a significant positive effect on Repurchase Intention and acts as a mediating variable in the relationship between Perceived Quality and Price Perception on Repurchase Intention. Thus, customer satisfaction is an important

factor in driving repurchase intent.

5.1 Recommendations

This research has several limitations that can be the basis for further research development. First, the next study is suggested to expand the distribution of the questionnaire by reaching more groups and communities on various platforms so that the participation of Glad2Glow brand moisturizer users on Shopee from various regions of Indonesia becomes wider and more representative. Second, the next research needs to improve the questionnaire instrument by adding questions about the type or variant of Glad2Glow moisturizer used by the respondents. Thus, the analysis of Perceived Quality, Price Perception, Satisfaction, and Repurchase Intention on each product variant can be carried out more comprehensively. Third, the scope of this research is still limited to customers who make purchases through Shopee. As a result, consumer behavior on other e-commerce platforms and offline purchases has not been covered, even though platform differences can affect perceptions of quality, price, satisfaction, and repurchase intent. Fourth, the research model can be developed by adding other variables such as brand image, customer trust, electronic word of mouth (e-WOM), perceived value, or customer experience so that the understanding of the factors that affect Repurchase Intention in skincare products becomes wider. With this development, it is hoped that Glad2Glow will be able to increase customer satisfaction, encourage repurchase intentions, and maintain competitiveness in the increasingly competitive skincare industry.

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